

The impact of alien fish removal operations on the macroinvertebrates of the Rondegat River

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Introduction

The Rondegat River is a foothill stream draining from the Cedarberg Mountains, which form part of the Cape Floristic Region, an area of critical global conservation concern (Darwall *et al* 2009). The Rondegat River contains five native fish species, all of which are drastically impacted by Smallmouth Bass (Woodford *et al* 2005). After the positive outcome of an environmental impact assessment, the application to use rotenone to remove the Smallmouth Bass in the Rondegat River was approved. Smallmouth Bass established in the lower reaches of this small river, up to the point of a natural waterfall barrier. Rotenone is a piscicide that is extremely effective in controlling fish populations (Britton & Brazier 2006, 2008). While effective for fish removal, the use of rotenone in river systems is controversial and has been shown to have a detrimental impact on some invertebrate communities (Vinson *et al* 2010). The aim of this study was to monitor the short-term effect of rotenone on the benthic macroinvertebrate community of the Rondegat River.

Materials & Methods

Three sample stations were selected within the rotenone treatment zone and three more above the waterfall barrier to serve as control sites, where only native fish were present. The areas were selected carefully to be comparable in-stream biotopes for the sampling of invertebrates. Four stones of comparable size were collected from stones-in-current biotope in order to calculate the density and diversity of invertebrate taxa per unit area. When each stone was collected, a 200 µm mesh kick-net was used to collect any fleeing invertebrates. Sampling of the stones was carried out one week before, one week after and two months after the alien fish removal operation. Invertebrate drift sampling was carried out using a 400x400 mm, 250 µm mesh net. On the day of treatment, drift was sampled at a single site simultaneously in both the treatment and control reaches. Samples were taken at 07h00, 09h00, 13h00 & 17h00 for 30 min per sample and continued on the following day. Depth and current velocity were measured at the mouth of the net and the amount of invertebrate drift was calculated per minute of water sampled.

Figure 1: Densities of four insect orders on stones sampled from the stones-in-current biotope.

Figure 2: Number of invertebrates collected by drift sampling during rotenone application and the day thereafter.

Figure 3: Proportional contribution of various drifting aquatic insect orders collected during the rotenone application

Results

The average abundance of individual Ephemeroptera per cm² of stone surface showed a significant decrease after the alien fish removal operation (Figure 1). There was no significant difference in abundance of Trichoptera, Coleoptera and Diptera. Two months after the application of rotenone, the abundance of Ephemeroptera had returned to levels comparable to the week before, while the Diptera showed a significant increase compared to both pre- and post-treatment sampling. During the alien fish removal, the plume of rotenone caused a catastrophic drift event (Figure 2) compared to drift recorded from the control sites at the same time. The number of drifting insects per unit time increased from near zero to almost a thousand. The proportion of invertebrates drifting was staggered based on sensitivity to the rotenone, where the Ephemeroptera and Plecoptera responded the fastest followed by the Coleoptera, the Diptera and then the Hemiptera (Figure 3). The remaining orders contributed a steady and similar proportion to the drift volume.

Conclusion

The use of rotenone for the removal of Smallmouth Bass from the Rondegat River had a severe immediate impact on the macroinvertebrate community in the lower reaches of the river. However, due to colonisation from upstream the proportional abundance of taxa had returned to a pre-treatment state within two months. This suggests that the invertebrate community could be resilient to the use of rotenone as a conservation management tool.

Drift net sampling in the control zone

Odonata (*Trithemis arteriosa*)

Treatment site

Ephemeroptera (*Afronurus peringueyi*)

References

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